

Bioactivity of *Sesbania grandiflora* against larvae of *Plutella xylostella* under laboratory conditions

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Abstract

Sesbania grandiflora, commonly known as Agathi, is a fast-growing and widespread medicinal plant that belongs to the family Fabaceae. The bioactive molecules of *S. grandiflora* exhibit various properties, such as antibacterial, antifungal and insecticidal activity. The current study investigated the toxicity of different solvent extracts of *S. grandiflora* on the second instar larva of *Plutella xylostella* under laboratory conditions. Extraction was done using two methods, namely, Soxhlet extraction and Cold maceration extraction. The toxicity of extracts was evaluated by comparing absolute and untreated controls in a completely randomized design. The impact on the larval weights due to the extracts from the two methods was studied, analyzed statistically, and documented. Among the two extraction techniques tested, the Soxhlet method of extraction proved to be effective, with higher mortality compared to the other extraction techniques. The ethanol-based extract exhibited complete mortality of *P. xylostella* on the seventh DAT (Day After Treatment) with reduced larval weights compared to the other treatments.

Keywords: *Sesbania*, extraction, *Plutella*, mortality, larval weights

Introduction

The diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), is the most notorious and serious insect pest causing damage to cruciferous crops worldwide with varying infestation levels according to the plant

type, locality and level of natural enemies. The insect pest is capable of causing 100% crop loss if no control measures are undertaken [1]. The widely used chemical control has become less effective against *P. xylostella* due to the rapid development of resistance to almost all groups of insecticides, including organochlorines, carbamates, pyrethroids, organophosphates, abamectin, pyrazoles, neonicotinoids, oxadiazines, insect growth regulators and *Bacillus thuringiensis* [2, 3]. The injudicious use of chemical insecticides has resulted in many ecological problems such as accumulation of toxic residues in the environment and hazards to mammals [4]. Therefore, the development of novel strategies for efficient management of *P. xylostella* without deleterious effects on the environment is required. Among the alternative methods, plants are versatile sources for insect pest management due to their selectivity and safety to non-target organisms and the environment. In addition, they are available easily and are low in cost compared to chemical insecticides [3, 5]. Natural products are promising alternatives with compounds comprising insecticidal activities [6, 7, 8]. Many of the native plant species have been evaluated against a wide range of insect pests on various crops [9]. A variety of plants consists of survival and defensive chemical strategies exhibiting insecticidal and antifeedant effects. The chemical diversity of plants includes active compounds with unknown modes of action against insect pests. Novel pesticides with new modes of action are necessary for delayed resistance development and to meet the stringent health and environmental regulations. *Sesbania grandiflora* L., commonly known as Agathi, is a widely available medicinal plant that belongs to the family Fabaceae [10]. The leaves are bitter and are rich in vitamin C, calcium, sterols, saponin, quercetin, myricetin, and kaempferol [11]. All parts of *S. grandiflora* are used in traditional medicine, and phytochemical investigations have been conducted on extracts of the leaves, seeds and roots of *S. grandiflora* to provide scientific validation of its properties [12]. *S. grandiflora* contains plenty of sterols, saponins, and tannins which are responsible for its insecticidal properties [13]. However, only a few studies have been conducted to study the insecticidal properties of *S. grandiflora*. The objective of the present study was to explore the insecticidal activity of *S. grandiflora* against second-instar larvae of *P. xylostella*.

Materials and methods

Collection and preparation of plant parts

Sesbania grandiflora leaves were collected from the fields of Agricultural College and Research Institute (AC&RI), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai, (Narasingham, Tamil Nadu – Lat N 9° 58' 33.4668", Long E 78° 12' 20.1132") during 2022. The plant materials were dried, pulverized, sieved, and stored in sealed vials under refrigerated conditions until preparation of the extracts, which were also stored at the same temperatures until in vitro tests. The *S. grandiflora* leaf powder was extracted with various solvents, hexane, ethyl acetate and ethanol, using two different extraction methods, namely, Soxhlet and cold maceration.

Cold maceration Extraction

Leaf powder of *S. grandiflora* was mixed with the respective solvent in a ratio of (1:10 w/v) in a conical flask. The mixture was stirred thoroughly with a glass rod and kept in a mechanical shaker with intermittent shaking for 72 hours. The mixture was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and concentrated using a rotary evaporator at 40°C, and the resultant residue was kept in a refrigerator till further use [14].

Soxhlet (continuous hot percolation) extraction

In the method, the *S. grandiflora* leaf powder was packed in a cellulose thimble and placed in the sample holder of the Soxhlet extractor with the respective solvent poured in the round-bottom flask in the ratio (1:10 w/v). A continuous hot percolation technique was done until the solvent in the sample holder appeared colorless. The final extract was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and concentrated to dryness using a rotary evaporator at 40°C. The content of extractable matter was calculated in mg/g using a digital weighing balance for recovery estimation and stored in the refrigerator until further use [15].

Mass culturing of test insect, Diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella*

Laboratory rearing of *P. xylostella* was initiated with the *Plutella xylostella* infested cauliflower curds collected from the vegetable market in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, and kept in adult emergence cages. The adults emerging from the infested curds were transferred to oviposition cages and provided with mustard seedlings for egg laying. The first instar larvae were reared on mustard leaves in larval rearing cages, and the later instars were transferred to fresh cauliflower leaves in small containers for easy handling and utilized for further studies. A part of the larval population was maintained until pupation to maintain the culture. Pupae were kept in Petri dishes inside adult emergence cages, and the emerged adults were fed with honey solution (10%) supplemented with Vitamin E capsules soaked in cotton to enhance the fecundity. The rearing cycle was continued to ensure constant availability of culture during the entire study period. The pupae were transferred to adult emergence cages, and mustard seedlings were provided for oviposition of adults [16].

Leaf dip bioassay for toxicity and impact on growth

A leaf dipping method described by Tabashnik and Cushing (1987) was followed to evaluate the insecticidal activity of the crude extracts of *S. grandiflora* leaf extracts in different solvents against *P. xylostella* [17]. The cauliflower leaf discs of (5cm dia) was placed in circular plastic containers of (7 mm dia) and lined with moist filter paper, in order to maintain the turgidity of the leaf discs. The toxicity and antifeedant bioassay of the leaf extracts was carried out using the leaf dip method under no-choice condition. The assay was carried out using a 5% concentration of the crude extract based on the results given by Sushmita *et al.* (2022) [18]. The cauliflower leaf discs were thoroughly washed, dried and sprayed with the test solutions (0.1% Triton X 100 was used as surfactant) for about 30 seconds to facilitate uniform active ingredient treatment. The leaf discs were placed in a slant position for about two minutes in a tray to drain the excess solution and then allowed to dry for about 30 minutes at room temperature. Ten-second instar larva of *P. xylostella* (pre-starved for 2 h) were transferred to the treated leaf and allowed for feeding. Observations were made on the number of dead larvae and larval weights until pupation and the percentage mortality was calculated using the formula

$$\text{Mortality (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of dead insects}}{\text{Total number of insects released}} \times 100$$

Results

Impact of different extracts of *S. grandiflora* on larval mortality of *P. xylostella*

On the first DAT, the highest larval mortality was observed in the treated check, which was statistically on par with the ethanol (Soxhlet) at 26.67% and 23.33% followed by ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) at 16.67%. On the second and third DAT, the highest larval mortality was recorded in ethanol (Soxhlet) with 60.00% and 76.67% followed by statistically similar results in the treated check with 43.33% and 66.67%, ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) with 40.00% and 60.00% and hexane (Soxhlet) with 33.33% and 50.00%. On the fourth DAT, the highest larval mortality was recorded as 83.33% in ethanol (Soxhlet) followed by 76.67% in the treated check. On the fifth and sixth DAT, a similar pattern of results was observed with the highest mortality of 86.67% in ethanol (Soxhlet) and treated check on all the days, followed by ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) with 63.33% on the fifth DAT and 66.67% on sixth DAT. Complete larval mortality was attained on the seventh DAT in the ethanol (Soxhlet) and the eighth DAT in the treated check. On the ninth DAT, highest larval mortality was recorded in ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) with 73.33%, while the larva of the untreated check entered pupation. On the 10th DAT, the highest mortality of 73.33% was observed in ethyl acetate (Soxhlet), followed by the other treatments. The lowest larval mortality was recorded in the aqueous extracts, which ranged from 6.67 to 26.67% (Table 1).

Impact of different extracts of *S. grandiflora* on larval weights of *P. xylostella*

On the first DAT, there was no significant difference among the treatments with larval weights ranging from 0.15 to 0.17 mg. On the second DAT, there was an increase in the larval weights with significant difference among the treatments with the lowest larval weight of 0.19 mg in the ethanol (Soxhlet) followed by 0.21 mg in the treated check. On the third DAT, the lowest larval weight was observed in the ethanol (Soxhlet) followed by the treated check with 0.20 mg and 0.27 mg. On the fourth and fifth DAT, lowest larval weights were recorded in ethanol (Soxhlet) with 0.31 mg and 0.44 mg which was statistically similar to the treated check with 0.34 mg and 0.43 mg. On the sixth DAT, lowest larval weight of 0.40 mg was recorded in the ethanol (Soxhlet) followed by 0.54 mg in the treated check and 0.59 mg in the ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) extract. On the seventh DAT, complete larval mortality was observed in the ethanol (Soxhlet) with 0.51 mg in the treated check and 0.64 mg in the ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) which was statistically on par. On the eighth DAT, complete larval mortality was observed in the treated check with the lowest larval weight in the ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) with 0.69 mg followed by statistically same weights in the hexane (Soxhlet) extract and ethanol (Cold maceration) with 0.75 mg and 0.78 mg respectively. On the ninth and 10th DAT, the untreated check entered pupation whereas the treatments observed a prolongation in the larval period with a reduced larval weight of 0.74 mg and 0.78 mg in the ethyl acetate (Soxhlet) followed by 0.82 mg and 0.89 mg in the hexane (Soxhlet) extract. It was notable that the larval weights were higher in the untreated check compared to the treatments (Table 2).

Discussion

The extracts obtained by adopting different extraction techniques were studied for their toxicity, antifeedant, and impact on growth and development. It was concluded that the extracts obtained via Soxhlet extraction caused comparatively higher mortality and lower larval weights than those obtained via cold maceration extraction. These results were in accordance with the study conducted by Tulashie *et al.* (2021) to

characterize and assess the toxicity of neem extracts obtained by two different methods to manage fall armyworm (FAW) invasion. The yields after extraction were 23.92% and 17.05% for neem seed oil extract (NSOE) and methanolic neem leaf extract (MNLE) obtained from neem seeds and leaves by Soxhlet extraction and cold maceration. The LC_{50} of 1.78%, 0.97%, and 0.68% was estimated for NSOE and LC_{50} of 2.67%, 2.62% and 1.64% for MNLE after 2, 6 and 12 hours respectively. It was concluded that NSOE had high pesticidal activity compared to MNLE indicating Soxhlet method of extraction as the best method for extraction with higher activity [14]. Sankeshwari *et al.* (2018) concluded that the solvent ethanol is polar, which results in the leaching of more active ingredients during extraction compared to other solvents, which may be a possible reason for higher mortality in the ethanol extract [19]. These results are in agreement with Sangavi *et al.* (2019) that the ethanol extracts showed a mortality of 40.00% at 0.4% concentration [19]. The reduction of larval weights is in accordance with the statement of Talukder (2006) that botanical pesticides have a detrimental effect on insect growth and development, diminishing the weight of larvae, pupae, and adults and extending the phases of development [20]. The digestibility in the larval stages is affected, leading to death overtime [21]. Therefore, the choice of the extraction technique is crucial to achieve better yields without compromising biological activities. Therefore, *S. grandiflora* leaf extracts prepared using the Soxhlet method was proven to have promising insecticidal activity against *P. xylostella*.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the Soxhlet method of extraction is capable of extracting bioactive molecules, causing higher mortality than the cold maceration technique in the polar solvent ethanol. Therefore, further studies have to be conducted to explore the possibilities of *S. grandiflora* extracts in managing *P. xylostella* as an alternative to synthetic pesticides.

References

- [1] M. Sarfraz, and B. A. Keddie, "Conserving the efficacy of insecticides against *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lep., Plutellidae)," *Journal of Applied Entomology*. Vol. 129, pp. 149-57, 2005.
- [2] D. S. Charleston, R. Kfir, M. Dicke, and L. E. Vet, "Impact of botanical pesticides derived from *Melia azedarach* and *Azadirachta indica* on the biology of two parasitoid species of the diamondback moth," *Biological control*. Vol.33, pp. 131-142, 2005.
- [3] L. Qian, G. Cao, J. Song, Q. Yin, and Z. Han, "Biochemical mechanisms conferring cross-resistance between tebufenozide and abamectin in *Plutella xylostella*," *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*. Vol. 91, pp. 175-179, 2008.
- [4] M. F. Khan, R. P. Griffin, G. R. Carner, and C. S. Gorsuch, "Susceptibility of diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae), from collard fields in South Carolina to *Bacillus thuringiensis*," *Journal of Agricultural and Urban Entomology*. Vol. 22, pp. 19-26, 2005.
- [5] G. M. Liang, W. Chen, and T. X. Liu, "Effects of three neem-based insecticides on diamondback moth (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae)," *Crop protection*. Vol. 22, pp. 333-340, 2003.

- [6] S. A. Ibrahim, G. Henderson, B.C. Zhu, H. Fei, and R. A. Laine, "Toxicity and behavioral effects of nootkatone, 1, 10-dihydronootkatone, and tetrahydronootkatone to the formosan subterranean termite (Isoptera: Rhinotermitidae)," *Journal of Economic Entomology*. Vol. 97, pp. 102-111, 2004.
- [7] A. R. Lax, and W. L. Osbrink, "United States Department of Agriculture—agriculture research service research on targeted management of the Formosan subterranean termite *Coptotermes formosanus* Shiraki (Isoptera: Rhinotermitidae)," *Pest Management Science: formerly Pesticide Science*. Vol. 59, pp. 788-800, 2003.
- [8] B. C. Zhu, G. Henderson, R.P. Adams, L. X. Mao, Y. Yu, and R. A. Laine, "Repellency of vetiver oils from different biogenetic and geographical origins against Formosan subterranean termites (Isoptera: Rhinotermitidae)," *Sociobiology*. Vol. 42, pp. 623-638, 2003.
- [9] R. Srinivasan, "Integrating biopesticides in pest management strategies for tropical vegetable production," *Journal of biopesticides*. Vol. 5, pp. 36-45, 2012.
- [10] K. Padmalochana, and M. D. Rajan, "Antimicrobial activity of Aqueous, Ethanol and Acetone extracts of *Sesbania grandiflora* leaves and its phytochemical characterization," *International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research*. Vol. 5, pp. 957-62, 2014.
- [11] R. A. Mustafa, A. A. Hamid, S. Mohamed, and F. A. Bakar, "Total phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and radical scavenging activity of 21 selected tropical plants," *Journal of food science*. Vol. 75, pp. 28-35, 2010.
- [12] A. K. Mohiuddin, "Medicinal and Therapeutic value of *S. grandiflora*," *International Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*. Vol. 4, pp. 18, 2019.
- [13] V. D. Wagh, K. V. Wagh, Y. N. Tandale, and S. A. Salve, "Phytochemical, pharmacological and phytopharmaceutics aspects of *Sesbania grandiflora* (Hadga): A review," *Journal of Pharmacy Research*. Vol. 2, pp. 889-892, 2009.
- [14] S. K. Tulashie, F. Adjei, J. Abraham, E. Addo, "Potential of neem extracts as natural insecticide against fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda* (JE Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)," *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering*. Vol. 4, pp. 100130, 2021.
- [15] I. Larkem, N. Tarai, N. Benchikha, M. Messaoudi, S. Begaa, M. Martins, and D. C. Pinto, "Chemical profile and antioxidant activity of *Sesbania bispinosa* (Jacq.) W. Wight aerial parts and seeds extracts," *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*. Vol. 45, pp. 15468, 2021.
- [16] P. R. Nithya, S. Manimegalai, S. Nakkeeran, and S. Mohankumar, "Comparative study of the ditrophic interaction between *Beauveria bassiana* and *Plutella xylostella*," *3 Biotech*. Vol. 11, pp. 1-15, 2021.
- [17] B. E. Tabashnik, and N. L. Cushing, "Leaf residue vs. topical bioassays for assessing insecticide resistance in the diamond-back moth, *Plutella xylostella* L.," *FAO Plant Protection Bulletin*. Vol. 35, pp. 11-14, 1987.

- [18] R. M. Sankeshwari, A. V. Ankola, K. Bhat, and K. Hullatti, "Soxhlet versus Cold Maceration: Which Method Gives Better Antimicrobial Activity to Licorice Extract Against: *Streptococcus Mutans*," Journal of the Scientific Society. Vol. 45, pp. 67-71, 2018.
- [19] R. Sangavi, and Y. J. Edward, "Anti-Insect activities of plant extracts on the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.)," International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences. Vol. 6, pp. 28-39, 2017.
- [20] A. Rahman, and F. A. Talukder, "Bioefficacy of some plant derivatives that protect grain against the pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus*," Journal of Insect Science. Vol. 6, pp. 3, 2006.
- [21] I. M. Padial, S. A. Souza, J. B. Malaquias, C.A. Cardoso, J.K. Pachu, C.A. Fioratti, and R. M. Mussury, "Leaf Extracts of *Miconia albicans* (Sw.) Triana (Melastomataceae) Prevent the Feeding and Oviposition of *Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae)," Agronomy. Vol. 13, pp. 890, 2023.

Table 1. Cumulative larval mortality of *P. xylostella* due to acute feeding on different extracts of *S. grandiflora* treated leaves

Treatments (Extracts out of combinations)		Mean cumulative larval mortality (%) ^{#S}									
Solvent	Method	1DAT	2DAT	3DAT	4DAT	5DAT	6DAT	7DAT	8DAT	9DAT	10DAT
T1 – Hexane extract (5%)	Soxhlet	6.67±0.58 (13.96) ^{bc}	33.33±1.15 (35.32) ^{ab}	50.00±0.00 (45.29) ^{ab}	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^c	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^{bc}	60.00±0.00 (51.06) ^{bc}	60.00±0.00 (51.06) ^{bc}	60.00±0.00 (51.06) ^{bc}	63.33±0.58 (53.07) ^{cd}	63.33±0.58 (53.07) ^{bc}
T2 – Ethyl acetate extract (5%)		16.67±0.58 (24.25) ^{ab}	40.00±1.00 (39.44) ^{ab}	60.00±1.00 (51.15) ^{ab}	60.00±0.00 (51.06) ^{bc}	63.33±0.58 (53.07) ^b	66.67±0.58 (55.09) ^b	66.67±0.58 (55.09) ^b	70.00±0.00 (57.10) ^b	70.00±0.00 (57.10) ^{bc}	73.33±0.58 (59.33) ^b
T3 – Ethanol extract (5%)		23.33±0.58 (29.12) ^a	60.00±1.00 (51.15) ^a	76.67±1.53 (62.30) ^a	83.33±0.58 (66.55) ^a	86.67±0.58 (69.30) ^a	96.67±0.58 (84.02) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a
T4 – Hexane extract (5%)	Cold	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	23.33±0.58 (29.12) ^{bc}	40.00±1.00 (39.44) ^{bc}	43.33±0.58 (41.44) ^c	46.67±0.58 (43.37) ^c	46.67±0.58 (43.37) ^c	50.00±0.00 (45.29) ^c	50.00±0.00 (45.29) ^c	53.33±0.58 (47.21) ^d	53.33±0.58 (47.21) ^c
T5 – Ethyl acetate extract (5%)		6.67±0.58 (13.96) ^{bc}	23.33±1.15 (28.65) ^{bc}	40.00±1.00 (39.44) ^{bc}	46.67±0.58 (43.37) ^c	50.00±0.00 (45.29) ^{bc}	53.33±0.58 (47.21) ^{bc}	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^{bc}	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^c	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^{cd}	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^{bc}
T6 – Ethanol extract (5%)		6.67±0.58 (13.96) ^{bc}	26.67±0.58 (31.32) ^b	46.67±0.58 (43.37) ^b	53.33±0.58 (47.21) ^c	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^{bc}	56.67±0.58 (49.14) ^{bc}	60.00±0.00 (51.06) ^{bc}	60.00±0.00 (51.06) ^{bc}	63.33±0.58 (53.07) ^{cd}	63.33±0.58 (53.07) ^{bc}
T7 – Aqueous extract (5%)		0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	6.67±0.58 (13.96) ^{cd}	20.00±1.00 (26.45) ^c	23.33±0.58 (29.12) ^d	26.67±0.58 (31.32) ^c	26.67±0.58 (31.32) ^d				
T8 – Azadirachtin 1 EC @ 2 ml/lit		26.67±0.58 (31.32) ^a	43.33±0.58 (41.44) ^{ab}	66.67±1.15 (55.31) ^{ab}	76.67±1.15 (62.08) ^{ab}	86.67±0.58 (69.30) ^a	93.33±0.58 (78.03) ^a	96.67±0.58 (84.02) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a	100.00±0.00 (90.00) ^a
T9 – Untreated check		0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^d	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^d	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^e	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	0.00±0.00 (4.05) ^c	Pupa	Pupa
SEd		0.95	1.11	1.00	0.60	0.51	0.51	0.43	0.39	0.50	0.45
F value		12.77	17.67	28.81	90.12	130.40	132.91	190.2	231.02	152.80	205.69
P value		0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**

[#]Mean values of three replications are represented as mean± standard deviation;

^SFigures in the parentheses are arc sine transformed values (x+0.5);

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other, by Tukey's test (p ≤ 0.05);

DAT- Days After Treatment; SEd: Standard Error of the difference;

** Highly Significant.

Table 2. Impact of Hexane extract of *S. grandiflora* on larval weight of *P. xylostella* due to acute feeding

Treatments (Extracts out of combinations)		Mean fresh weight of the larvae (mg) ^{#@}									
Solvent	Method	1DAT	2DAT	3DAT	4DAT	5DAT	6DAT	7DAT	8DAT	9DAT	10DAT
T1 – Hexane extract (5%)	Soxhlet	0.16±0.03 (0.81) ^a	0.23±0.07 (0.85) ^{bc}	0.37±0.05 (0.93) ^c	0.50±0.05 (1.00) ^b	0.55±0.10 (1.02) ^b	0.62±0.07 (1.06) ^c	0.73±0.08 (1.11) ^b	0.75±0.08 (1.12) ^b	0.82±0.13 (1.15) ^b	0.89±0.15 (1.18) ^b
T2 – Ethyl acetate extract (5%)		0.15±0.01 (0.81) ^a	0.23±0.04 (0.85) ^{bc}	0.45±0.03 (0.97) ^{dc}	0.49±0.07 (0.99) ^b	0.53±0.10 (1.01) ^b	0.59±0.12 (1.04) ^b	0.64±0.13 (1.07) ^a	0.69±0.12 (1.09) ^a	0.74±0.12 (1.11) ^a	0.78±0.13 (1.13) ^a
T3 – Ethanol extract (5%)		0.15±0.03 (0.81) ^a	0.19±0.05 (0.83) ^a	0.20±0.05 (0.84) ^a	0.31±0.10 (0.90) ^a	0.44±0.12 (0.97) ^a	0.40±0.12 (0.97) ^a	Dead	Dead	Dead	Dead
T4 – Hexane extract (5%)	Cold	0.16±0.03 (0.84) ^c	0.36±0.07 (0.93) ^c	0.48±0.05 (0.99) ^c	0.55±0.05 (1.02) ^c	0.67±0.10 (1.08) ^c	0.73±0.07 (1.11) ^d	0.81±0.08 (1.14) ^c	0.89±0.08 (1.18) ^c	0.97±0.13 (1.21) ^c	1.12±0.15 (1.27) ^c
T5 – Ethyl acetate extract (5%)		0.16±0.03 (0.83) ^{bc}	0.29±0.07 (0.89) ^d	0.41±0.05 (0.95) ^{cd}	0.58±0.05 (1.04) ^c	0.64±0.10 (1.07) ^c	0.69±0.07 (1.09) ^c	0.77±0.08 (1.13) ^{bc}	0.83±0.08 (1.15) ^c	0.89±0.13 (1.18) ^d	0.98±0.15 (1.22) ^d
T6 – Ethanol extract (5%)		0.17±0.03 (0.82) ^{ab}	0.25±0.07 (0.87) ^c	0.38±0.05 (0.94) ^c	0.53±0.05 (1.01) ^b	0.57±0.10 (1.03) ^b	0.65±0.07 (1.07) ^c	0.76±0.08 (1.12) ^{bc}	0.78±0.08 (1.13) ^b	0.85±0.13 (1.16) ^c	0.92±0.15 (1.19) ^c
T7 – Aqueous extract (5%)		0.15±0.03 (1.00) ^d	0.38±0.01 (1.11) ^f	0.86±0.05 (1.17) ^f	0.94±0.09 (1.20) ^d	1.48±0.16 (1.41) ^d	1.69±0.24 (1.48) ^c	2.21±0.24 (1.65) ^d	2.93±0.24 (1.85) ^d	3.35±0.24 (1.96) ^f	3.84±0.24 (2.08) ^f
T8 – Azadirachtin 1 EC @ 2 ml/lit		0.16±0.02 (0.81) ^a	0.21±0.03 (0.84) ^{ab}	0.27±0.01 (0.88) ^b	0.34±0.05 (0.92) ^a	0.43±0.03 (0.96) ^a	0.54±0.06 (1.02) ^a	0.51±0.06 (1.02) ^a	Dead	Dead	Dead
T9 – Untreated check		0.15±0.05 (1.10) ^c	0.49±0.02 (1.18) ^g	0.98±0.02 (1.22) ^g	1.73±0.01 (1.49) ^c	2.46±0.03 (1.72) ^c	3.82±0.03 (2.08) ^f	4.62±0.06 (2.26) ^c	4.93±0.01 (2.33) ^c	Pupa	Pupa
Sed		0.004	0.005	0.008	0.007	0.004	0.011	0.009	0.010	0.004	0.011
F value		1015.86	1078.90	525.32	1225.43	6536.09	2345.24	5669.09	4722.03	15533.47	2867.05
P value		0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**	0.0001**

[#]Mean values of three replications are represented as mean ± standard deviation

[@]Figures in the parentheses are square root transformed values

Mean followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other by Tukey's test ($p \leq 0.05$)

DAT – Days After Treatment; SED: Standard Error of the difference

** Highly significant